

Modified Mishra Distribution

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Abstract :

The proposed distribution, is a single parameter continuous probability distribution and has been introduced for statistical modeling of survival time data, is a modified form of Mishra distribution and hence, it is named as “Modified Mishra Distribution (MMD)”. Sah (2015) obtained Mishra distribution (MD) and it has been observed that, in most of the cases, it is a better alternative of Lindley (1958) distribution (LD). Recently, Sah (2022) has obtained Quadratic-exponential distribution (QED) and it has been observed that it gives better fit to the data sets, of similar nature, than MD and LD. All the required characteristics such as probability mass function, cumulative probability distribution, probability generating function and mode of MMD have been obtained. Moments about the mean and about origin have been discussed. The Hazard rate function, Reliability function and the mean residual life function of MMD have been discussed. The estimation of parameter has been discussed by the method of moments as well as the maximum likelihood method. Goodness of fit has been applied to some over-dispersed data-sets and the obtained value Chi-square of MMD has been compared with LD, MD and QED.

Keywords : Mishra distribution, Lindley distribution, Moments, Over-dispersion, Estimation, Goodness of fit.

1. Introduction :

Statistics literature is full of countable and continuous probability distributions with wide range of applications in social and physical sciences. Research is an endless process because there is always some chance to add some new concepts and new visions on the previously obtained research work by others. Mishra distribution (MD)^[4] was proposed by Sah (2015) and its probability density function (pdf) was given by

$$f_1(y) = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} (1 + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y} \quad (1)$$

Where, $\alpha > 0$ and $y > 0$. It has been obtained for a better alternative of Lindley distribution (LD)^[2] of similar kind of data-sets, given by its pdf

$$f_2(y) = \frac{\alpha^2}{(1 + \alpha)} (1 + y)e^{-\alpha y}; \alpha > 0, y > 0 \quad (2)$$

was obtained by Lindley (1958)^[2]. It can be observed that both distributions have a single parameter and have been applied to the similar nature of over-dispersed data-sets. Research is an endless process and we always keen to find a better alternative of previous one. In this way, Sah (2022) obtained Quadratic-exponential distribution (QED)^[5] given by its pdf

$$f_3(y) = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\alpha^3 + \alpha + 2)} (\alpha + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y}; \alpha > 0, y > 0 \quad (3)$$

It has been observed that QED^[5] is a better alternative of LD^[2] as well as MD^[4]. It has also been observed that LD^[2] is better for modeling of survival life time data when there is moderate variation in observed data-sets and poor alternative when there is a very low or high variation in observed data-sets. The proposed continuous probability distribution has also a single parameter and has been introduced as a better alternative of LD^[2], MD^[4] and QED^[5] for statistical modeling of survival life time over-dispersed data-sets, having low or moderate or high variations, of similar

nature. The proposed distribution is a modified form of MD^[4] and hence, it is named as Modified Mishra Distribution (MMD) which is a single parameter continuous probability distribution introduced as a better alternative of LD^[2], MD^[4] and QED^[5] for statistical modeling of survival life time data. Probability density functions, cumulative probability distribution function, moment generating function and mode of MMD have been obtained. Statistical moments about the mean as well as about origin have been obtained. Nature of the proposed distribution has been discussed on the basis of dispersion, Skewness and kurtosis; the hazard rate function, the mean residual life time and reliability function have been discussed. Goodness of test has been applied to some previously used data by others.

2. Material and Methods :

The proposed distribution is based on the core concept of continuous probability distribution which contains a single parameter. It starts with the basic characteristics such as probability density function, cumulative probability distribution function, moment generating function and mode of this distribution have been obtained. Moments about the mean as well as about origin have been obtained. Parameter of MMD has been estimated by the method of moments and the maximum likelihood method. Nature of the distribution has been discussed according to dispersion, Skewness and kurtosis. Goodness of fit has been applied to some over-dispersed data-sets to test validity of the theoretical work and ending with concluding remarks about MMD.

3. Results :

The results obtained about MMD are classified under following sub-headings.

- 3.1 Modified Mishra Distribution (MMD) and Related Characteristics
- 3.2 Moments of MMD
- 3.3 Estimation of Parameters and
- 3.4 The Hazard Rate Function, Reliability Function and The Mean Residual Life Function.

3.1 Modified Mishra Distribution (MMD) and Related Characteristics :

It is a modified form of MD^[4] and hence, it is named as Modified Mishra Distribution (MMD). It is a single parameter continuous probability distribution which follows all the basics of continuous probability distribution. Let a continuous random variable Y follows MMD with parameter α and its probability density function (pdf) is obtained as

$$f(y) = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} (\pi + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y} \tag{4}$$

Where, $y > 0$ and $\alpha > 0$. The expression (4) is the pdf of MMD.

Probability distribution function (cdf) of the MMD : It can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} F(Y) = P(Y \leq y) &= \int_0^y f(y)dy = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \int_0^y (\pi + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y} dy \\ &= 1 - e^{-\alpha y} - \frac{\alpha y(2 + \alpha + \alpha y)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha y} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The expression (5) is the cdf of the MMD (4). Graphical representations of probability density function (pdf) and cumulative distribution function (cdf) for varying values of parameter are given below.

Fig. 1 : Graph of pdf at $\alpha = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$

Fig. 2 : Graph of pdf of MMD at $\alpha = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

Fig. 3 : Graph of cdf of MMD at $\alpha = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$

Fig. 4 : Graph of cdf of MMD at $\alpha = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

Mode of MMD :

Let Y be a MMD variate. Mode is the value of Y at which pdf of MMD (4) is maximum. For maxima $f'(y) = 0$ and $f''(y) < 0$. To get the expression for mode, differentiate the expression (4) with respect to y , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dy} [f(y)] &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \frac{d}{dy} [(\pi + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y}] \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} [(\pi + y + y^2)(-\alpha e^{-\alpha y}) + e^{-\alpha y}(1 + 2y)] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Applying $f'(y) = 0$, we get

$$[(\pi + y + y^2)(-\alpha e^{-\alpha y}) + e^{-\alpha y}(1 + 2y)] = 0$$

Or, $\alpha y^2 + (\alpha - 2)y + (\alpha\pi - 1) = 0$ (7)

Solving the Quadratic equation (7), we get

$$y = \frac{(2 - \alpha) \pm \sqrt{[(\alpha - 2)^2 - 4\alpha(\alpha\pi - 1)]}}{2\alpha} \quad (8)$$

Differentiate the expression (6) with respect to y , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dy} \left[\frac{d[f(y)]}{dy} \right] &= \frac{d}{dy} \left[\frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} [(\pi + y + y^2)(-\alpha e^{-\alpha y}) + e^{-\alpha y}(1 + 2y)] \right] \quad (9) \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[(\pi + y + y^2)(\alpha^2 e^{-\alpha y}) + (-\alpha e^{-\alpha y})(1 + 2y) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \alpha(1 + 2y)e^{-\alpha y} + 2e^{-\alpha y} \right] \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[(\pi + y + y^2)(\alpha^2 e^{-\alpha y}) - 2\alpha(1 + 2y)e^{-\alpha y} + 2e^{-\alpha y} \right] < 0 \\ &= \left[\alpha^2(\pi + y + y^2) - 2\alpha(1 + 2y) + 2 \right] < 0 \quad \text{if } 0 < \alpha < 0.588073 \text{ for the} \\ &\text{expression (8).} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Moment Generating Function [$M_Y(t)$] : It is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} M_Y(t) &= E(e^{ty}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{ty} f(y) dy = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \int_0^{\infty} e^{ty} (\pi + y + y^2) e^{-\alpha y} dy \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \int_0^{\infty} (\pi + y + y^2) e^{-(\alpha-t)y} dy \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[\pi \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(\alpha-t)y} dy + \int_0^{\infty} y e^{-(\alpha-t)y} dy + \int_0^{\infty} y^2 e^{-(\alpha-t)y} dy \right] \end{aligned}$$

After a little simplification, we get

$$= \frac{\alpha^3}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \left[\frac{\pi(\alpha - t)^2 + (\alpha - t) + 2}{(\alpha - t)^3} \right] \quad (11)$$

The expression (11) is the M.G.F. of MMD (4).

3.2 Moments of MMD :

In this section, we have been discussed about

- The r^{th} moment about origin
- The first four moment about the mean and
- Dispersion, Skewness and Kurtosis of the proposed distribution.

The r^{th} moment about origin: It can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_r &= E[Y^r] = \int_0^{\infty} y^r f(y) dy = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[\int_0^{\infty} y^r (\pi + y + y^2) e^{-\alpha y} dy \right] \quad (12) \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[\pi \int_0^{\infty} y^r e^{-\alpha y} dy + \int_0^{\infty} y^{r+1} e^{-\alpha y} dy + \int_0^{\infty} y^{r+2} e^{-\alpha y} dy \right] \\ &= \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \left[\frac{\pi \Gamma(r+1)}{\alpha^{(r+1)}} + \frac{\Gamma(r+2)}{\alpha^{(r+2)}} + \frac{\Gamma(r+3)}{\alpha^{(r+3)}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

After a little simplification, we get

$$\mu'_r = \frac{r!}{\alpha^r} \left[\frac{\{\pi\alpha^2 + (r+1)\alpha + (r+2)(r+1)\}}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \quad (13)$$

The expression (13) is the r^{th} moment about origin of MMD (4). Substituting the value of $r = 1, 2, 3, 4$ in the expression (13), the first four moments about origin can be given by

$$\mu'_1 = \frac{1!}{\alpha^1} \left[\frac{\{\pi\alpha^2 + (1+1)\alpha + (1+2)(1+1)\}}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\mu'_2 = \frac{2!}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{\{\pi\alpha^2 + (2+1)\alpha + (2+2)(2+1)\}}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] = \frac{2!}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \quad (15)$$

$$\mu'_3 = \frac{3!}{\alpha^3} \left[\frac{\{\pi\alpha^2 + (3+1)\alpha + (3+2)(3+1)\}}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] = \frac{3!}{\alpha^3} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \quad (16)$$

$$\mu'_4 = \frac{4!}{\alpha^4} \left[\frac{\{\pi\alpha^2 + (4+1)\alpha + (4+2)(4+1)\}}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] = \frac{4!}{\alpha^4} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 5\alpha + 30)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \quad (17)$$

Central Moments of MMD :

The first four moments about the mean of the MMD (4) can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1 &= 0 \\ \mu_2 &= \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2 = \frac{2!}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right]^2 \\ &= \left[\frac{\{2(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) - (\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)^2\}}{\{\alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)\}^2} \right] \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

$$\mu_3 = \mu'_3 - 3\mu'_2\mu'_1 + 2(\mu'_1)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{3!}{\alpha^3} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] - 3 \left[\frac{2!}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \right] \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \\
 &\quad + 2 \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right]^3 \\
 &= \left[\frac{\{6(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)^2 - 6(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + 2(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)^3\}}{\{\alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)\}^3} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

(19)

$$\mu_4 = \mu_4' - 4\mu_3'\mu_1' + 6\mu_2'(\mu_1')^2 - 3(\mu_1')^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{4!}{\alpha^4} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 5\alpha + 30)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] - 4 \left[\frac{3!}{\alpha^3} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \\
 &\quad + 6 \left[\frac{2!}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] \right] \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right]^2 - 3 \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right]^4 \\
 &= \left[\frac{\left\{ 24(\pi\alpha^2 + 5\alpha + 30)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)^3 - 24(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)^2 \right\}}{\{\alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)\}^4} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

(20)

To analyze nature of the proposed distribution according to dispersion, we have been obtained Index of dispersion (I), Co-efficient of Variation (C.V.) and the condition at which the proposed distribution is Equi-dispersed, Over-dispersed and Under-dispersed for a specific value of the parameter of MMD.

$$I = \frac{\text{Variance}}{\text{Mean}} = \frac{(\pi^2\alpha^4 + 4\pi\alpha^3 + 16\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha^2 + 12\alpha + 12)}{[\alpha(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)]} \quad (21)$$

If ' I ' is equal to one, the distribution is said to be Equi-dispersed. If ' I ' is greater than one, the distribution is said to be Over-dispersed. If ' I ' less than one, the distribution is said to be Under-dispersed.

It has been observed that MMD will be Equi-dispersed when $\alpha = 1.422085337$, Over-dispersed when $\alpha < 1.422085337$ and Under-dispersed when $\alpha > 1.422085337$.

$$C.V. = \left(\frac{\sigma_Y}{\mu'_1} \right) 100 = \left[\frac{\sqrt{(\pi^2\alpha^4 + 4\pi\alpha^3 + 16\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha^2 + 12\alpha + 12)}}{[\alpha(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)]} \right] 100 \quad (22)$$

The expression (22) is the co-efficient of variation of MMD (4). To know about nature of MMD according to shape and size we have obtain co-efficient of skewness and kurtosis as follows.

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\mu_3}{\mu_2^{3/2}} = \frac{(2\pi^3\alpha^6 + 12\pi^2\alpha^5 + 60\pi^2\alpha^4 + 12\pi\alpha^4 + 84\pi\alpha^3 + 72\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha^3 + 36\alpha^2 + 72\alpha + 48)}{(\pi^2\alpha^4 + 4\pi\alpha^3 + 16\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha^2 + 12\alpha + 12)} \quad (23)$$

It has been observed that $(2/\sqrt{3}) < \gamma_1 < \infty$. Hence, MMD (4) is positively skewed in shape.

$$\beta_2 = \frac{\mu_4}{\mu_2^2} = \left[\frac{\left\{ 24(\pi\alpha^2 + 5\alpha + 30)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)^3 - 24(\pi\alpha^2 + 4\alpha + 20)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)^2 + 12(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)^2(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) - 3(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)^4 \right\}}{\{2(\pi\alpha^2 + 3\alpha + 12)(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) - (\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)^2\}^2} \right] \quad (24)$$

It has been obtained that $5 < \beta_2 < \infty$ and hence MMD is leptokurtic in size.

3.3 Estimation of Parameter :

The proposed distribution is based on a single parameter (α). To estimate the parameter, we apply only two methods. The first one is the method of moments and the second is the method of maximum likelihood.

(a) The Method of Moments :

The first moment about origin of MMD (4) is required to obtain an estimate of the parameter (α). Using the expression

$$\mu'_1 = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{(\pi\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right]$$

We get

$$\mu' \alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi \alpha^2) - (\pi \alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6) = 0 \tag{25}$$

The expression (25) is the third-degree polynomial equation in α . Replacing the population mean by the sample mean and solving the expression (25) by the Newton-Rapson or Regula-Falsi method, we get an estimated value of α for the implemented data-set.

(b) The Method of Maximum Likelihood :

Let (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) be a sample of size n drawn from a population of size N which follows MMD (4). The likelihood function of MMD (4) can be obtained as

$$L = \prod_{i=1}^n f(y_i; \alpha) = \left(\frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi \alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \right)^n \left[\prod_{i=1}^n (\pi + y_i + y_i^2) \right] e^{-n\alpha \bar{y}} \tag{26}$$

The log likelihood equation is

$$\text{Or, } \ln L = n \ln(\alpha)^3 - n \ln(2 + \alpha + \pi \alpha^2) + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(\pi + y_i + y_i^2) - n\alpha \bar{y} \tag{27}$$

Differentiation of the log likelihood equation with respect to α , we get

$$\text{Or, } \frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{3n}{\alpha} - \frac{n(1 + 2\pi \alpha)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi \alpha^2)} - n\bar{y} = 0$$

$$\text{Or, } \bar{y} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{(\pi \alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi \alpha^2)} \right] \tag{28}$$

$$\text{Or, } \bar{y} \alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi \alpha^2) - (\pi \alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 6) = 0 \tag{29}$$

The expression (28) is the mean of MMD. Putting the value of the sample mean in the expression (29) and solving the equation for α , we get an estimate of α .

3.4 The Reliability Function, Hazard Rate Function and Mean Residual Life Function :

The Reliability Function :

It is widely used in manufacturing sector to fix a guaranty or warranty period of products because it measures probability of survival lifetime without failure in a certain interval of time or we can say that the probability of time taken by a product for first failure. Let Y denotes a continuous random variable of survival life time of a component and the probability that component will survive until time ‘ t ’ is called reliability function denoted by $R(t)$ and it is given by

$$R(t) = P(Y > t) = \int_t^{\infty} f(y)dy = 1 - F(t) = \frac{[(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + \alpha t(2 + \alpha + \alpha t)]}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha t} \quad (30)$$

At, $t = 0$, $R(t) = 1$ then the component of the system is said to be perfect reliable to work properly. At $t = \infty$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} [R(t)] = 0$. Hence, we can say that the value of reliability function decreases as working time of the system increases and vice-versa. i.e., $R(t) \propto 1/t$.

Fig. 5 : Graph of $R(t)$ of MMD at $\alpha = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$

Fig. 6 : Graph of $R(t)$ of MMD at $\alpha = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

The Hazard Rate Function :

Hazard measures the conditional probability of a failure given that the system is working. The failure density (pdf) measures the overall speed of failures. Hazard rate or Instantaneous failure rate measures the dynamic speed of failures. For a continuous distribution with p.d.f. $f(y)$ and c.d.f. $F(y)$, the hazard rate function (also known as failure rate function) and the mean residual life function are respectively defined as

$$h(y) = \lim_{\Delta y \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(Y < y + \Delta y / Y > y)}{\Delta y} = \frac{f(y)}{1 - F(y)} \tag{31}$$

The main reason for defining the $h(y)$ is that it is more convenient to work with than $f(y)$. Putting the value of $f(y)$ and $1 - F(y)$ in the expression $h(y)$, the Hazard rate function of QED (4) has been obtained as

$$h(y) = \frac{f(y)}{R(t)} = \frac{\alpha^3(\pi + y + y^2)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + \alpha y(2 + \alpha + \alpha y)} \tag{32}$$

The failure rate function of MMD (4) until time ‘ t ’ is thus obtained as

$$h(y=t) = \frac{\alpha^3(\pi + t + t^2)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + \alpha t(2 + \alpha + \alpha t)} \tag{33}$$

$$\text{At } t=0, h(y=t=0) = \frac{\pi\alpha^3}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \tag{34}$$

It is also obvious that $h(y)$ is an increasing function of y and α .

Mean Residual Life Function :

In reliability studies, the expected additional life time given that a component has survived until time ‘ t ’ is called mean residual life time. Let a random variable Y denotes the life of a component, the mean residual life function is given by

$$m(y) = E[Y - y / Y > y] = \frac{\int_y^\infty [1 - F(t)] dt}{1 - F(y)} \tag{35}$$

To obtain $m(y)$ of the MMD (4), we have to calculate the following measures

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(Y) = P(Y \leq y) &= \int_0^y f(y)dy = \frac{\alpha^3}{(\pi\alpha^2 + \alpha + 2)} \int_0^y (\pi + y + y^2)e^{-\alpha y} dy; x > 0, \phi > 0 \\
 &= 1 - e^{-\alpha y} - \frac{\alpha y(2 + \alpha + \alpha y)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha y}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $f(y)$ and $F(y)$ are the probability density function and probability distribution function of MED (4).

$$1 - F(y) = \frac{[(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + \alpha y(2 + \alpha + \alpha y)]}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha y} \tag{36}$$

$$1 - F(t) = e^{-\alpha t} + \frac{\alpha t(2 + \alpha + \alpha t)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha t} \tag{37}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_y^\infty \{1 - F(t)\} dt &= \int_y^\infty \left[e^{-\alpha t} + \frac{\alpha t(2 + \alpha + \alpha t)}{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} e^{-\alpha t} \right] dt \\
 &= \left[\frac{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + (4 + \alpha + 4\alpha y + \alpha^2 y + \alpha^2 y^2)}{\alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} \right] e^{-\alpha y} \tag{38}
 \end{aligned}$$

Putting the value of $\int_y^\infty [1 - F(t)] dt$ and $1 - F(y)$ in equation (35), the mean residual life function has been obtained as

$$m(y) = \frac{(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + (4 + \alpha + 4\alpha y + \alpha^2 y + \alpha^2 y^2)}{\alpha[(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2) + \alpha y(2 + \alpha + \alpha y)]} \tag{39}$$

$$\text{At } y = 0, m(y = 0) = \frac{(6 + 2\alpha + \pi\alpha^2)}{\alpha(2 + \alpha + \pi\alpha^2)} = \mu'_1 \tag{40}$$

It can also be seen that at $y = 0$, the mean residual life function is the mean of MMD (4). It can also be seen that $m(y)$ is a decreasing function of y and α .

4. Applications :

To test validity of the theoretical work, the fitting of MMD (4) has been applied to the following to data.

Example (1) : Survival times (in days) of guinea pigs infected with virulent tubercle bacilli, reported by Bjerkedal (1960)^[1]

Survival Time (in days)	0-80	80-160	160-240	240-320	320-400	400-480	480-560
Observed frequency	8	30	18	8	4	3	1

Example (2) : Mortality grouped data for blackbirds species reported by Paranjpe and Rajarshi (1986)^[3]

Survival Time (in days)	0-1	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	7-8	>8
Observed frequency	192	60	50	20	12	7	6	3	2

The expected frequencies according to the LD^[2], MD^[4], QED^[5] have also been given, for ready comparison with those obtained by the MMD, in the following tables.

Table I : Expected Vs Observed of Example (1)

Survival Time (in days)	Observed frequency	Expected frequency			
		Lindley	Mishra	QED	MMD
0-80	8	16.1	10.8	10.8	10.8
80-160	30	21.9	24.8	24.8	24.8
160-240	18	15.4	19.0	19.0	19.0
240-320	8	9.0	10.1	10.1	10.1
320-400	4	5.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
400-480	3	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
480-560	1	2.3	1.0	1.0	1.0
Total	72	72.0	72.0	72.0	72.0
$\hat{\alpha}$		0.011	0.016431	0.016519	0.016514
$\chi^2(df)$		7.7712(3)	1.98(3)	1.98(3)	1.98(3)
$\mu'_1 = 181.11111$		$\mu'_2 = 43911.11111$			

Table II : Expected Vs Observed Frequencies of Example (2)

Survival Time (in days)	Observed frequency	Expected frequency			
		LD	MD	QED	MMD
0-1	192	173.5	142.8	145.9	165.0
1-2	60	98.6	104.5	101.2	83.3
2-3	50	46.5	58.7	57.6	51.9
3-4	20	20.1	27.5	27.5	27.4
4-5	12	8.1	11.5	12.0	13.4
5-6	7	3.2	4.5	4.8	6.2
6-7	6	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.8
7-8	3	0.4	0.5	0.7	1.2
>8	2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.8
Total	352	352.0	352.0	352.0	352.0
$\hat{\alpha}$.984	1.311017	1.269721	1.10616888
$\chi^2(df)$		49.85(4)	46.37(4)	39.64(4)	17.60(5)
$\mu'_1 = 1.56818$		$\mu'_2 = 5.005682$			

From table (I), we can observe that the value of Chi-square of MMD is less than the LD^[2] and is equal to the MD^[4] and QED^[5] with same degrees of freedom. From table (II), we can observe that the value of Chi-square of MMD is less than LD^[2], MD^[4] and QED^[5].

5. Concluding Remarks :

In this paper, several structural properties such as probability density function, function, distribution function, moment generating function and mode have been obtained. The moments about origin as well as the mean have been derived. To estimate the parameter of this distribution, the method of moments and the maximum likelihood have been applied and discussed. The reliability function, hazard rate function and mean residual life function have been obtained and discussed. The highlighted remarks about the MMD (4) are

- * It has been observed that it will be Equi-dispersed when, $\alpha = 1.422085337$, over-dispersed when $\alpha < 1.422085337$ and Under-dispersed when $\alpha > 1.422085337$.
- * It has been observed that $(2/\sqrt{3}) < \gamma_1 < \infty$. Hence, it is positively skewed in shape.
- * It has been obtained that $5 < \beta_2 < \infty$ and hence it is leptokurtic in size.
- * From tables I and II, it has been observed that (a) it is a better alternative of LD^[2] (b) equal and better alternative of MD^[4] and QED^[3] under statistical homogeneity.

Conflict of Interest :

The author has declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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